

Integrated Electro-Thermal-Ageing Modelling Framework for Second-Life Lithium-Ion Batteries in Stationary Applications

Huma Iqbal*
H.Iqbal-2@sms.ed.ac.uk
University of Edinburgh
Edinburgh, United Kingdom

Dr. Zafar Iqbal
Zafar.Iqbal@ed.ac.uk
University of Edinburgh
Edinburgh, United Kingdom

Dr. Jonathan Shek
J.Shek@ed.ac.uk
Senior Lecturer, University of Edinburgh
Edinburgh, United Kingdom

Prof. Aristides Kiprakis
Aristides.Kiprakis@ed.ac.uk
Professor, University of Edinburgh
Edinburgh, United Kingdom

Abstract

With the increasing adoption of electric vehicles (EVs), a growing number of lithium-ion batteries are reaching their end-of-life (EOL). These retired batteries, commonly referred to as second-life batteries (SLBs), retain approximately 70–80% of their original capacity and present significant potential for reuse in stationary storage systems. This paper presents a comprehensive integrated electro-thermal-ageing modelling framework for both new and SLBs, which incorporates an electrical model, a modified ageing model and a simplified thermal model suitable for long-term simulations. The models are validated for three widely used EV battery chemistries: LFP, NMC, and NCA. The framework is extended to SLBs by incorporating degraded capacity, adjusted operational constraints, and SOH-aware battery management strategies. Two case studies—a hybrid PV-battery system and an off-grid PV-battery system—are simulated over a five-year period using real-world data. Results demonstrate that SLBs can provide reliable and cost-effective energy storage when operated under controlled conditions, supporting sustainable energy systems and circular economy goals.

Keywords

Second life batteries, Battery modelling, Stationary storage applications, Renewable integration, MATLAB

1 Introduction

The rapid growth of EVs has led to an increase in retired lithium-ion batteries. Although these batteries no longer meet the performance requirements for EV applications, they typically retain 70–80% of their

initial capacity, making them viable candidates for second-life applications in stationary energy storage systems. The reuse of SLBs offers both environmental and economic benefits. It reduces battery waste, delays recycling processes, and lowers the cost of energy storage systems [2]. However, several challenges hinder their widespread adoption, including uncertainties in degradation behaviour, lack of first-life operational data, and absence of standardized battery management strategies[1].

Existing studies often treat battery electrical, thermal, and ageing behaviour independently, limiting their applicability for realistic system-level analysis. Also, simplified degradation assumptions and lack of long-term simulations under real operating conditions reduce the reliability of these approaches. This work addresses these challenges by proposing an integrated modelling framework that combines electrical, thermal, and ageing models with a degradation-aware battery management system (BMS) to estimate battery state-of-health (SOH). The framework is applicable to both new and SLBs and enables accurate long-term performance assessment.

2 Integrated Modelling Framework

The proposed framework integrates three key components: battery equivalent electrical model, ageing model (cyclic + calendar) and simplified thermal model. These models are embedded with an application layer representing real operating conditions, including renewable generation, load demand, and ambient temperature. The BMS regulates charging and discharging currents based on these inputs and other operational constraints such as battery SOC, initial SOH, voltage and temperature. The outputs include key performance indicators such as battery SOH, temperature, and voltage, presenting battery behaviour continuously under realistic long-term simulations.

2.1 Battery Electrical Model

The electrical behaviour of the battery is modelled using a Thevenin equivalent circuit [2], incorporating open-circuit voltage (OCV) and internal resistance as shown in Figure 1.

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Figure 1: First order Thévenin equivalent model of a battery

Where, V_{oc} is open circuit voltage, R_b is battery internal resistance, V_{bat} is terminal voltage and I_b is battery current. The following equation holds for the estimation of battery terminal voltage.

$$V_{bat} = V_{oc} - I_b R_b$$

The model is designed for computational efficiency by focusing on steady-state behaviour rather than transient dynamics.

2.1.1 Battery Selection

The selection of battery chemistry is essential for developing a generalized electrical model and to adapt to market trends. In this work, three widely used lithium-ion chemistries are considered: **Battery 1:** lithium iron phosphate (LFP), **Battery 2:** lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide (NMC), and **Battery 3:** lithium nickel cobalt aluminium oxide (NCA). These chemistries are selected due to their widespread adoption in EV applications and their distinct electrochemical characteristics, particularly in terms of voltage profiles, energy density, and degradation behaviour.

Table 1: Lithium-ion battery chemistries in EVs: market share & cost (2022–2024) [3]

Battery chemistry	Market Share in EVs	Pack Cost (USD/kWh)
	2024	2024
LFP (LiFePO ₄)	~40–45%	\$135
NMC (LiNiMnCoO ₂)	~50–55%	\$140
NCA (LiNiCoAlO ₂)	~10–12%	\$150
Others (LMO, LCO, etc.)	<5%	N/A

2.1.2 Modelling methodology

A framework is shown for battery electrical modelling using Thévenin equivalent circuit and battery datasheets [4] [5] [6] in Figure 2 which outlines the key steps involved in estimating the battery terminal voltage. SOC is defined as battery usable capacity and it is estimated through battery voltage.

Battery electrical parameters are derived from manufacturer discharge characteristics, which provide voltage–capacity curves at different current rates. The discharge capacity is first converted into SOC by normalizing with the rated capacity. Using these curves, open-circuit voltage (OCV) and internal resistance are extracted at different SOC levels through curve fitting. The relationship between SOC and OCV is then established using polynomial fitting, which effectively captures the nonlinear behaviour of lithium-ion batteries while maintaining computational simplicity. Similarly, the variation of

internal resistance with SOC is approximated using a second-order polynomial, reflecting its typical nonlinear trend. Finally, these relationships are implemented within a Thévenin equivalent circuit model and validated against manufacturer discharge curves under various C-rates, ensuring the accuracy of the electrical model for subsequent simulations.

Figure 2: Flowchart of battery modelling framework

The validation curves for selected battery chemistries are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Validation of discharge characteristics for selected batteries at given C-rates and temperature from datasheet

2.2 Generalized SOC–OCV Relationship

A key component of the electrical model is the relationship between state-of-charge and open-circuit voltage. Since this relationship varies across different lithium-ion chemistries, a generalized SOC–OCV model is developed in this work to enable multi-chemistry applicability. A flowchart of proposed method is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Flowchart for a generalized battery OCV-SOC relationship

Discharge curves for LFP, NMC, and NCA batteries are normalized and fitted using a polynomial function to obtain a unified representation of the SOC–OCV relationship. The generalized model is then scaled using nominal voltage values to represent specific battery types. While this approach provides a good approximation across different chemistries, minor deviations are observed in LFP batteries as illustrated in Figure 5 due to their flat voltage plateau and hysteresis characteristics.

Figure 5: Comparison of Normalized Battery Voc Curves with Fitted Generic Polynomial

Although a generic SOC–OCV relationship simplifies battery modelling, its accuracy is limited due to variations across lithium-ion chemistries, temperature dependence, non-equilibrium operating effects (such as polarization, hysteresis, and IR drop), and ageing-induced shifts in battery behaviour [7]. Overall, the model achieves sufficient accuracy for long-term simulation purposes.

3 Ageing Model

Battery degradation is modelled by incorporating both cyclic and calendar ageing mechanisms, which together determine the long-term SOH of the battery. A structured modelling approach is adopted to capture the influence of operating conditions such as depth of discharge (DoD), C-rate, temperature, and internal resistance.

3.1 Cyclic Ageing model

Cyclic ageing refers to degradation caused by repeated charge–discharge cycling and is a dominant factor limiting lithium-ion battery lifetime. It is driven by mechanisms such as SEI layer growth, lithium plating, and loss of active material, leading to capacity fade and increased internal resistance [8]. The degradation rate is strongly influenced by operating conditions including C-rate, depth of discharge (DoD), SOC window, and temperature.

A modified cyclic ageing model based on [9] is adopted, which captures the nonlinear effects of C-rate, temperature, and DoD. The capacity fade is expressed as:

$$\Delta Q_{cyc} = M(c) \exp\left(\frac{-Ea(c)}{RT}\right) (Ah)^z$$

where Ah represents throughput defined as cycle number × DoD × battery capacity, and the exponential term accounts for temperature dependence via Arrhenius behaviour. For analysis, the model is linearized as:

$$\ln(Q_{cyc}) = \ln(B) - \left(\frac{Ea}{RT}\right) + z \ln(Ah)$$

The model parameters are obtained from regression analysis, where the slope gives the power factor $z=0.55$, and activation energy varies with C-rate. The final form of the model is given as:

$$Q_{cyc} = 30,330 \exp\left(\frac{-31,500 + 370 * C_rate}{8.414T}\right) (Ah)^{0.55}$$

The model is validated for LiFePO₄ (2.2 Ah, 26650) cells at C/2 and 60°C across different DoD values, as shown in Figure 6, and further tested across multiple C-rates and chemistries. Validation results for LFP and NCA batteries are presented in Figure 7 demonstrating good agreement with datasheet cycle characteristics.

Figure 6: Capacity retention at 60°C and a discharge rate of C/2 plotted as a function of cycle number

Figure 7: cycle life validation for LFP and NCA chemistries using ageing model

Minor discrepancies are observed, primarily due to the exclusion of calendar ageing and the constant temperature assumption. In practice, aged batteries exhibit increased thermal sensitivity due to higher internal resistance and degradation, leading to accelerated ageing and higher heat generation.

3.2 Calendar Ageing model

Calendar ageing refers to battery degradation during storage or idle conditions and is primarily governed by parasitic side reactions between electrodes and electrolyte [10]. The degradation rate accelerates at elevated temperatures and high SOC levels due to increased electrochemical instability. Previous studies have shown that calendar ageing can be significant, particularly under high SOC storage conditions [10]. Due to the complexity of underlying electrochemical processes, semi-empirical models are widely used, incorporating Arrhenius temperature dependence and power-law time behaviour [11]. The SOC-dependent equation is given by:

$$Q_{cai}(t, T, SOC) = \alpha \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-E_a}{RT}\right) \cdot (t)^\beta \cdot (\gamma \cdot SOC + \delta)$$

where $\alpha=2.15 \times 10^{-4}$, $E_a=36.36\text{kJ/mol}$, $\beta=0.789$, $\gamma=1.19 \times 10^{-4}$ and $\delta=0.01$.

The model is derived from experimental data on NMC/graphite cells under multiple SOC and temperature conditions, showing good agreement for storage durations up to ~288 days. It is validated against experimental data, as shown in Figure 8, demonstrating accurate prediction of SOC and temperature dependent capacity loss over time. Parameter values vary across chemistries, but the adopted formulation provides a practical and computationally efficient representation for system-level simulations.

Figure 8: Validation of Calendar aging model for the SOC and temperature-dependent capacity loss over the time

The total degradation is obtained by combining calendar and cyclic ageing contributions:

$$Q_{total}(t) = Q_{cai}(t) + Q_{cyc}(t)$$

4 Modifying Electrical and Aging Models for Simulating SLBs

The developed electrical and ageing models are developed for new batteries and their direct application to SLBs is not appropriate; therefore, specific modifications are introduced to make them applicable to both new and SLBs, illustrated in Figure 9. The initial capacity is adjusted to reflect degraded SOH (typically ~80%), and this

updated capacity is used in SOC and terminal voltage calculations. Additionally, operational constraints are imposed by limiting the DoD, with a recommended range of 30–100% SOC to reduce further degradation. Charge/discharge current profiles are also controlled to limit stress on the battery, ensuring safe and efficient operation under degraded conditions.

Figure 9: A flow diagram to show recommended modifications in current system suited for second life batteries

Furthermore, ageing and temperature effects on internal resistance are incorporated into the electrical model to reflect performance degradation over time. The EOL resistance is estimated to be 1.6 to 2 times the resistance at the beginning of the studies [12]. The increase in resistance with cycle number and temperature [13] is modelled using these two equations:

$$R_T = 0.0002x^2 - 0.0372x + 1.7711$$

$$Factor_{Resistance} = 0.0365noc^3 - 0.3548noc^2 + 1.3544noc + 1.0363$$

Where x is temperature and noc is number of cycles. These factors are used to dynamically update internal resistance, capturing the combined impact of ageing and operating conditions on battery performance.

5 Thermal Model

Temperature is a critical parameter in battery degradation modelling and is explicitly integrated into the ageing model to capture its effect on performance decay. A simplified single-cell thermal model is adopted in this study based on [14], as shown in Figure 10 along with equations, to estimate battery temperature during operation.

Figure 10: Thermal model representation for a battery cell

$$\begin{aligned} mC_{cell} \frac{dT_{cell}}{dt} &= Q_p + Q_s - Q_B \\ Q_p &= I^2 R_b \\ Q_s &= T_{cell} \frac{I \Delta S}{F} \\ Q_B &= Ah (T_{cell} - T_{amb}) \end{aligned}$$

The model incorporates key parameters such as internal resistance, entropy coefficient (SOC-dependent), and heat transfer coefficient, enabling dynamic temperature estimation under varying operating conditions. Model validation is performed using a LiFePO₄ (2.2 Ah, 26650) cell under constant discharge rates of 0.5C, 1C, and 2C. The simulated temperature closely matches experimental results from, with an error of less than 1°C, as shown in Figure 11. The results confirm that temperature increases with C-rate due to higher ohmic losses, highlighting the importance of thermal management in preventing accelerated degradation and ensuring safe operation.

Figure 11: Single cell thermal model validation (constant discharge current)

For system-level applications, a simulation-based approach is adopted to extend the model to battery modules and packs. This approach avoids the need for extensive sensor deployment while providing scalable and computationally efficient temperature estimation suitable for battery management systems. A simplified methodology is employed in which a single-cell thermal model is used to predict pack-level temperature through a correction factor, significantly reducing computational effort while maintaining acceptable accuracy across varying operating conditions.

6 Case Studies

To evaluate the proposed integrated electrical, thermal, and ageing modelling framework, two case studies are considered: (i) a hybrid PV–battery microgrid system and (ii) an isolated PV–battery system. Both systems are modelled using real load demand and solar generation profiles over a simulation period of 5 years to analyse long-term battery performance and degradation.

Table 2: Battery and PV sizing for both cases for avg. load demand 10.8 kWh/day and 45V system. (Backup time 24h for HPVS and 48h for OPVS)

Application	PV Array Size (kWp)	Battery Configuration	Nominal Capacity (Ah)	Energy (kWh)
Hybrid PV-Battery system	4.5	2s × 2p Tesla 5.3 kWh (4 modules)	≈ 471	Nominal ≈ 21.2 At 70% DoD ≈ 14.8
Off-grid PV-battery system	6.5	2s × 3p (6 modules)	≈ 696	Nominal ≈ 31.8 At 70% DoD ≈ 22.3

The PV–battery systems are sized based on load demand, required autonomy, and operational constraints. The PV array is selected to meet the average load demand while ensuring sufficient energy availability for battery charging. The battery capacity is determined to supply the load during periods of low or no solar generation, while maintaining operation within safe SOC and DoD limits. For SLBs, additional capacity is incorporated to compensate for reduced SOH (≈80%) and stricter operating constraints. The resulting system configurations for both case studies are summarised in Table 2.

6.1 Hybrid PV–Battery System (HPVS)

The hybrid PV–battery system consists of a photovoltaic generation unit, battery storage, and grid connection, allowing bidirectional power exchange. The battery operates to balance generation and demand, while the grid provides support during peak load conditions and excess generation periods. The system is simulated under realistic operating conditions, where the battery is subjected to varying charge/discharge cycles depending on solar availability and load demand. The proposed electrical, thermal, and ageing models are integrated to evaluate battery performance over time.

The SOH degradation over time for new and both SLBs estimated using the proposed integrated modelling framework in shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: SOH loss and cumulative number of cycles over five years for HPVS using a new battery and SLBs with 80% and 65% initial SOH.

The results indicate that SLBs exhibit a stable degradation trend when operated within defined limits. The presence of grid support reduces the frequency and depth of cycling, thereby lowering degradation stress. Over the 5-year simulation period, the SOH of SLBs remains within acceptable limits and shows performance comparable to new batteries with only marginal additional capacity fade.

6.2 Off-Grid PV–Battery System (OPVS)

The isolated PV–battery system operates without grid support, where the battery serves as the sole energy storage component to meet load demand. This configuration results in higher cycling frequency and deeper discharge conditions compared to the hybrid system. The system is modelled using the same load and generation profiles, with the battery subjected to increased operational stress. The integrated modelling framework is used to capture the combined effects of electrical behaviour, thermal variation, and ageing.

Figure 13 illustrates that SLBs experience higher degradation compared to the hybrid case due to increased cycling. However,

when operated within the recommended DoD and current limits, the SOH remains within acceptable bounds over the simulation period. This demonstrates that SLBs can be effectively deployed in isolated systems, if appropriate operational constraints are maintained.

Figure 13: SOH loss and cumulative number of cycles over five years for OPVS using a new battery and SLBs with 80% and 65% initial SOH

6.3 Discussion

The results highlight that battery degradation in stationary storage systems is governed more by operating conditions than by initial battery state. The proposed framework demonstrates that parameters such as depth of discharge, C-rate, and temperature collectively define the degradation trajectory, rather than any single factor in isolation.

A key observation is that system-level design plays a crucial role in shaping these operating conditions. The interaction between PV generation and load demand directly influences battery cycling patterns, which in turn impacts ageing. Therefore, appropriate sizing and control strategies are essential to avoid excessive cycling stress and thermal buildup. The integrated modelling approach enables simultaneous evaluation of electrical behaviour, thermal response, and degradation, providing a more realistic representation of long-term battery performance. This is particularly important for second-life batteries, where variability in initial condition can be mitigated through controlled operation.

Overall, the findings suggest that second-life battery viability is not solely dependent on residual capacity, but on how effectively the system is designed and managed to operate within safe limits.

7 Conclusion and future work

This paper presents an integrated electrical, thermal, and ageing modelling framework for evaluating new and second-life lithium-ion batteries in stationary storage applications. The proposed model captures key degradation effects and enables long-term performance assessment under realistic operating conditions. Results from case studies show that SLBs can operate effectively when properly sized and controlled, with performance strongly dependent on operating conditions rather than initial state-of-health alone.

Future work will focus on experimental validation and real-time implementation in battery management systems, along with improved modelling of uncertainty in second-life battery characteristics and large-scale deployment scenarios.

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